

Evaluation of battery minerals flotation process eco friendliness utilising biodegradable lignin reagents

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ABSTRACT – As copper (Cu), nickel (Ni) and cobalt (Co) are main components of the Li-ion batteries, rising demand from the battery sector will “have a disruptive impact” over the next 10 years. There is a high need for replacing existing flotation reagents with more-environmentally friendly products. An efficient, sustainable lignin-based flotation concept for the selective extraction of base metals, such as Cu, Ni, Co and Au is proposed in the framework of “Batterflai” EIT funded project. This work presents environmental impact of the life cycle of lignin reagents for the preparation and use. The results will prepare the ground for integrating the natural, biodegradable lignin to flotation processes.

Keywords: Life Cycle Assessment, Lignin, Eco-friendly Reagents

INTRODUCTION

Froth flotation is a mineral processing that selectively separates the valuable minerals from each other and the gangue. The flotation method takes advantage of mineral hydrophobicity. Different types of reagents contribute to achieving the desired separation. Xanthates are commonly used as collector reagents in this process; however, they are characterised by health and environmental risks due to their toxicity. The urge for a green and sustainable transition in industry generates the need for total or partial

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replacement of such reagents. The development of a lignin-based reagent serves in this direction.

Lignin is a low-cost material that can be found in abundant amounts as it occurs from natural terrestrial organic material, such as forest residues, side streams of the pulp industry, and secondary ethanol production. Wood pulping and other biorefinery industries extract more than 50 million tonnes of lignin annually, whereas the total worldwide production is approximately 100 million tonnes annually [1, 2]. Thus, only about 2% is recovered for utilisation in applications.

The two prevailing categories of lignin are lignosulphonate and kraft lignin. Organosolv lignin (OL), that account for about 2%, is a new category that gains ground due to its high quality and purity [3]. OL from the pre-treatment of birch and spruce wood chips was used as the raw material for the preparation of micro- and nanoparticles to be used as lignin-based flotation reagents [4].

This study aims to quantify and evaluate the environmental impact of the newly-developed lignin-based flotation reagent. For reaching this, a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) analysis, is implemented. LCA is a technique used to assess the environmental impact of a product or system through its life cycle. The cradle-to-gate model that was developed, considers the different processes applied from the phase of birch and spruce wood chips to the final phase of nanoparticle reagent production. The processing method applied is under the case study applied in the framework of "BATTERY minerals using lignin nanoparticles as FLOTATlon collectors – BATTERFLAI" project.

EXPERIMENTAL

Organosolv pre-treatment of lignocellulosic biomass and particle preparation

Two types of biomasses have been used for this study, Norway spruce (*Picea abies L.*) and silver birch (*Betula pendula L.*) in form of woodchips. The biomass was milled before the pre-treatment to pass a 1 mm screen. The organosolv pre-treatment is performed using biomass, ethanol, and water mixture of 50% (birch) or 60% v/v (spruce). The biomass slurry is heated and after the pre-treatment, the slurry is filtered to recover solid pre-treated biomass and the hemicellulose-rich liquid that contains dissolved lignin. Lignin is recovered by precipitation due to ethanol removal by evaporation. Three separate fractions, cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin, are obtained as a result of the organosolv pre-treatment [5]. The purity of the lignin recovered exceeds 94% in both birch and spruce samples.

Table 1. Organosolv pre-treatment mixture and processes conditions

	Birch	Spruce
Biomass	110g	110g
Ethanol	1.1L	1.1L
Water mixture	50%	60%
Heat (autoclave reactors)	183°C – 1h	183°C – 1h

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Table 2. Sample concentration and recovery

		Birch	Spruce
Untreated sample (concentration)	Cellulose	35.2%	39.3%
	Hemicellulose	28.0%	30.5%
	Lignin	26.1%	28.1%
Pre-treated sample recovery		61.0%	72.0%
Pre-treated sample (concentration)	Cellulose	62.2%	50.3%
	Hemicellulose	3.0%	13.2%
	Lignin	16.0%	23.7%
Lignin recovery (raw organosolv lignin)		44.7%	37.5%
Lignin purity		>95%	>94%

The nanoparticles were prepared from raw OL by solvent exchange method. The 5% w/v lignin was dissolved in 75% v/v ethanol solution and mixed for 8h. Subsequent homogenization was performed at 750 bars, by using an APV-2000 homogenizer (SPX FLOW, Charlotte, NC, USA). The homogenized lignin solution was diluted with distilled water in ratio of 1:6, which caused the nanoparticle formation. OL nanoparticles were obtained as a dry powder after freeze-drying process [6].

In the same line, the microparticles were prepared from 1% w/v lignin in 75% v/v ethanol solution, which was mixed for 8h and homogenized. After homogenization, the ethanol was slowly removed by distillation. The decreasing concentration of ethanol triggered the formation of microparticles. OL microparticles were obtained as a dry powder after the freeze-drying process [6].

LCA Methodology

Goal and scope definition

The goal of this study was the quantification of the environmental impact of OL particles reagent production from birch and spruce bark. The pre-treatment of the biomass and the preparation of OL particles reagent were analysed.

Functional Unit

Functional unit (FU) provides the reference to which all inputs and outputs data in the assessment are normalised. In the study presented, the FU is 1kg of OL reagent produced.

System Boundary

A cradle-to-gate approach was adopted. The model was investigated in two phases, i) the pre-treatment of biomass and ii) the particles production. All inputs (biomass, electricity, water, chemicals, etc.), and outputs (pre-treated biomass, raw OL, recovered liquids, etc.) responding to each phase, were included within the system boundaries. The biomass used in the study was birch and spruce bark and the reagents generated were micro- and nanoparticle reagents.

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As a result, four models were assessed. Both birch and spruce feedstock used for the lignin production were considered to be wastes of forest industry eliminating the harvesting emissions they might carry. Besides, was considered that the lignin production and reagent preparation facility are located near a sawmill. Thus, no transportation regarding the bark and the OL were required.

Table 3 Four scenarios assessed

Model	Scenario
Nano-Birch OLN	S1
Nano-Spruce OLN	S2
Micro-Birch OLN	S3
Micro-Spruce OLN	S4

Life Cycle Inventory (LCI)

In this section, LCI information regarding the processes followed for the production of the OL reagents. The LCI for implementation of this study is based on the data acquired from the laboratory process.

Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA)

The LCIA quantifies the environmental impacts using the results of the LCI analysis and the impact factors. The mass of the environmental load is associated with the FU.

The impact categories selected to evaluate the four scenarios are: i) Climate change, default, excl. biogenic carbon (kg CO₂ eq.), ii) Freshwater ecotoxicity (FEP) (kg 1,4-Db eq.), iii) Human toxicity, cancer (kg 1,4-Db eq.) (HTP), iv) Photochemical Ozone Formation, Human Health (kg NO_x eq.) (POFP), v) Terrestrial ecotoxicity (kg 1,4-Db eq.) (TEP).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

Spruce biomass and birch biomass are pre-treated for the reagents; production. Raw OL is the output of the biomass pre-treatment and it is followed by further treatment in order to create the nano- and micro- reagent. The outcomes resulting from the evaluation and modelling of the four scenarios for the production of the OL reagents are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. LCIA results per 1kg of OL reagent produced

Impact Category	S1	S2	S3	S4
Climate change, default, excl. biogenic carbon (kg CO ₂ eq.)	164	174	133	187
FEP (kg 1,4-Db eq.)	0.097	0.102	0.059	0.071
HTP (kg 1,4-Db eq.)	1.630	1.760	2.220	3.660
POFP (kg NO _x eq.)	0.358	0.375	0.225	0.277

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TEP (kg 1,4-Db eq.)	113	119	65.5	75.9
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The greatest environmental impact of OLN reagent preparation comes from the grid electricity consumed mainly in the process of nano- or microparticles formation. The formation of nanoparticles requires more energy than microparticles formation affecting almost all the impact categories. On the other hand, spruce biomass pre-treatment requires more ethanol production, affecting the HTP.

Discussion

Lignin is a low-cost material that can be found in abundant amounts as forest residues or side product of other processes. OL, have the advantage to be sulphur-free in comparison with kraft lignin. That gives the opportunity to be explored as the basis for the production of reagents that can be utilized in flotation process.

The production of an environmentally friendly reagent that can efficiently enter in the mine industry and specifically in the beneficiation process replacing partially xanthates reagent can contribute to improve the impact of beneficiation process. Therefore, different methods are implemented to develop a novel, promising reagent.

CONCLUSION

The utilisation of lignin, for generating a product that may replace a harmful for both health and environment material, as xanthates complies with the targets to reach a more environmentally friendly and sustainable industry. In this framework, four scenarios have been implemented for the production of an OLN reagent.

The LCA presented in this paper examined the impact of each scenario to evaluate the environmental burden of each of the four proposed solutions and to detect the hot spots that requires improvement. As results, the electricity consumed for particles formation is responsible for the main part of reagents impact, especially in the case of nanoparticle reagent.

It is important to mention that this study is based on laboratory data. An LCA implemented based on laboratory data gives a limited indication of the industrial scale production environmental impact. However, it serves to give environmental guidance for the emerging product. The impact of the product in a large-scale production process can be significantly lower than in laboratory scale.

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REFERENCES

1. Bajwa, D.S., et al., *A concise review of current lignin production, applications, products and their environmental impact*. Industrial Crops and Products, 2019. **139**: p. 111526.
2. *The Global Market for Lignin 2023-2033*. 2023; Available from: <https://www.giiresearch.com/report/fmi1223534-global-market-lignin.html>.
3. Shrotri, A., H. Kobayashi, and A. Fukuoka, *Chapter Two - Catalytic Conversion of Structural Carbohydrates and Lignin to Chemicals*, in *Advances in Catalysis*, C. Song, Editor. 2017, Academic Press. p. 59-123.
4. Hrzová, K., et al., *Organosolv lignin hydrophobic micro- and nanoparticles as a low-carbon footprint biodegradable flotation collector in mineral flotation*. Bioresource Technology, 2020. **306**: p. 123235.
5. Nitsos, C., et al., *Isolation and Characterization of Organosolv and Alkaline Lignins from Hardwood and Softwood Biomass*. ACS Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering, 2016. **4**(10): p. 5181-5193.
6. Matsakas, L., et al., *Preparation of low carbon impact lignin nanoparticles with controllable size by using different strategies for particles recovery*. Industrial Crops and Products, 2020. **147**: p. 112243.